

Question	SPARQL query
Is there some reusing of other existing datasets?	?sub dmp:reusingData ?obj.
If yes, what is their provenance?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dcat:qualifiedRelation ?relation . ?relation dc:relation ?reusedDataset . ?reusedDataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?reusedDataset dc:description ?obj .
If yes, what are they used for?	?project rdf:type foaf:Project . ?project dmp:hasObjective ?objective . ?datasetRelation dmp:fulfillObjective ?objective . ?dataset dc:relation ?datasetRelation .
If yes, how many datasets are reused?	SELECT (COUNT(*) AS ?count) WHERE { ?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dcat:qualifiedRelation ?relation . ?relation dc:relation ?reusedDataset . ?reusedDataset dc:description ?obj . }
What type of data will be generated	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dcat:theme ?concept. ?concept dc:description ?description .
What will be the format of generated data?	?distribution rdf:type dcat:Distribution . ?distribution dc:format ?obj . ?obj ?pro ?sub .
What are the objectives of the project/research?	?project rdf:type foaf:Project . ?project dmp:hasObjective ?objective . ?objective dc:description ?objectiveDescription .
What data volume will be generated?	?distribution rdf:type dcat:Distribution . ?distribution dcat:byteSize ?volume .
What type of persistent identifier will be used?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset datacite:hasIdentifier ?id . ?id datacite:usesIdentifierScheme ?identifierScheme .
What metadata scheme will be used to describe data?	?metadataDocument rdf:type fabio:MetadataDocument . ?metadataDocument datacite:usesMetadataSchema ?scheme . ?scheme dc:description ?schemeDescription .
What metadata elements will be used to describe data?	?metadataDocument rdf:type fabio:MetadataDocument . ?metadataDocument dmp:containsMetadataElement ?element .
What is the name of the data repository?	?distribution rdf:type dcat:Distribution . ?distribution dcat:accessService ?repository .
Is the data repository trusted?	?distribution rdf:type dcat:Distribution . ?distribution dcat:accessService ?repository . ?repository dmp:isTrusted ?obj.

Is embargo applied to data?	?datasetEmbargo rdf:type dmp:Embargo . ?datasetEmbargo dmp:isEmbargoApplied ?embargo .
Will the data be made openly available?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dmp:hasAvailability ?datasetAvailability . ?datasetAvailability dmp:accessibility ?datasetAccessibility . ?datasetAccessibility dcs:dataAccess ?access .
Will metadata be made openly available?	?metadata rdf:type fabio:Metadata . ?metadata dmp:hasAvailability ?metadataAvailability . ?metadataAvailability dmp:accessibility ?metadataAccessibility . ?metadataAccessibility dcs:dataAccess ?access .
For who is the data usable for?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dmp:isUseableFor ?thirdParty . ?thirdParty ?pred ?obj .
What are the restriction criteria for access the data?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dmp:hasAvailability ?datasetAvailability . ?datasetAvailability dmp:accessibility ?datasetAccessibility . ?datasetAccessibility dmp:accessCriteria ?criteria .
What will be the cost of making data FAIR?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset schema:estimatedCost ?cost . ?cost sioc:topic ?topic . ?topic dc:description ?topicDescription . ?cost schema:value ?value . FILTER regex(str(?topic), "FAIR") .
Does the data contain personnel information?	?dataset rdf:type dcat:Dataset . ?dataset dcs:personalData ?obj .